

From Dust to Phytoplankton: Research Priorities for Atmospheric-Ocean Iron Coupling

Workshop Sponsors

We gratefully acknowledge the sponsors whose support made this workshop possible. Funding was provided by the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) through the Atmospheric Chemistry Program (AGS-2438642) and the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) (OCE-2513154).

Opening Statement: In 1988, oceanographer John Martin made a provocative declaration that would reshape our conversations on ocean biogeochemistry research priorities: "Give me a half tanker of iron, and I will give you an ice age." His insight – that iron limits ocean productivity across vast regions and thereby controls atmospheric CO₂ through biological carbon sequestration – has driven nearly four decades of research into marine iron cycling. Yet despite this sustained effort, our ability to predict how natural atmospheric iron inputs affect ocean ecosystems remains remarkably limited. Current Earth system models cannot reliably simulate biological responses to observed modern dust deposition events, undermining confidence in projections of how changing aerosol patterns will affect future ocean carbon uptake under climate change.

This white paper synthesizes findings and recommendations from the [Iron at the Air-Sea Interface Workshop](#), held July 28-31, 2025 in Asheville, North Carolina. The hybrid workshop convened atmospheric scientists, chemical oceanographers, biological oceanographers, and biogeochemical modelers to assess current knowledge and identify critical research priorities. The workshop revealed fundamental gaps spanning laboratory measurements, field observations, mechanistic understanding, and model capabilities – gaps that prevent us from answering basic questions about how atmospheric deposition influences ocean productivity. With dust emissions projected to shift substantially—though with considerable uncertainty in both sign and magnitude across climate scenarios—wildfires increasing in frequency and intensity, and anthropogenic aerosol patterns shifting as economies evolve, closing these gaps has become urgent.

The research agenda outlined here is comprehensive, spanning mechanistic process studies, coordinated observational networks, model intercomparison projects, and next-generation satellite missions. This scope is commensurate with one challenge: transforming Martin's qualitative insight into quantitative predictions that can inform Earth system models and climate projections. The investments required are substantial, but they are modest compared to the stakes – understanding a fundamental control on ocean productivity and carbon cycling that operates at planetary scales and shapes climate feedbacks that will determine the trajectory of global change.

Executive Summary

The Challenge: Despite nearly a century of inquiry – from Hart and Gran's early observations of iron-deficient "desolate zones" in the 1930s to John Martin's provocative iron hypothesis in the late 1980s – Earth system models still lack the capability to reliably predict how atmospheric iron and other trace element inputs affect ocean productivity and carbon cycling. With dust emissions, wildfires, and anthropogenic aerosols all changing under human pressure and climate warming, this longstanding knowledge gap increasingly undermines our ability to robustly project future ocean-climate feedbacks.

The Workshop: 55 atmospheric scientists, oceanographers, and modelers from 13 countries convened in July 2025 through a hybrid format – combining in-person participation in Asheville, North Carolina with online attendees – along with asynchronous discussion sessions. This inclusive approach brought together participants to identify critical barriers and chart a coordinated research roadmap for atmospheric-ocean iron research over the next 5-10 years.

Key Findings:

- **Models often break when reality is most dynamic:** Atmospheric and ocean biogeochemical models struggle to capture extreme aerosol events – dust storms, wildfires, and volcanic eruptions – which may drive disproportionate short-term biological responses. The relative importance of episodic versus continuous inputs depends on timescale, and models poorly represent both.
- **Missing mechanisms:** Models require organic ligands to maintain iron bioavailability but lack mechanistic understanding of ligand sources and cycling.
- **Lost in translation:** Atmospheric scientists measure "solubility", but ocean models need "bioavailability." These terms aren't equivalent, and inconsistent laboratory protocols result in orders-of-magnitude variability in solubility measurements, complicating cross-study synthesis.
- **Observational blind spots:** Current satellite retrievals cannot directly constrain dust deposition fluxes, bioavailable iron, or surface microlayer processes where initial aerosol-ocean interactions occur. Direct flux measurements in the open ocean remain rare, and long-term monitoring records are limited.
- **Scale mismatches occur at two levels:** Observational networks outside dedicated time-series sites often miss the short, episodic deposition pulses that drive surface-ocean biological responses (days to weeks). Although models can simulate deposition and ocean biogeochemistry at hourly or daily resolution, long-duration simulations typically save output at coarser intervals, smoothing over the short episodic pulses that may matter most biologically.
- **Scale-aware modeling is essential:** Ocean iron models span a wide range of scales, each suited to distinct scientific questions – from zero-dimensional kinetic models to global Earth system models. Inconsistencies arise not from intrinsic structural mismatches, but from misalignment between model configuration and the processes under investigation. Jointly designed atmospheric and ocean modeling frameworks are needed to address this.

Priority Actions Required:

1. **Establish process-based understanding** rather than parameter tuning – bring experimentalists and modelers into close collaboration to translate mechanisms into robust model representations

2. **Deploy integrated observing systems** combining satellites, autonomous platforms, long-term monitoring stations, and research vessels to capture the full pathway from atmospheric emission to biological utilization in the ocean
3. **Develop a Model Intercomparison Project** leveraging CMIP7 to create standardized trace element deposition fields for the broad community use.
4. **Create translation frameworks** between atmospheric chemistry measurements and the needs of the ocean biogeochemistry community and research priorities, with minimum reporting standards enabling cross-study synthesis
5. **Focus on climate-sensitive regions** where changing deposition patterns, increasing stratification, and environmental stress are expected to fundamentally alter ocean productivity.

Investment Needed: The research agenda spans laboratory experimentation, sustained in situ observations, satellite missions, and modeling infrastructure. This scope matches the challenge: transforming qualitative understanding into quantitative, predictive capability for planetary-scale processes that shape the Earth's climate.

The Stakes: Atmospheric deposition represents one of the largest external nutrient sources to open oceans. Without understanding this fundamental control on marine productivity and carbon sequestration, we cannot project how ocean ecosystems will respond to accelerating global change, including the associated increase in extreme events. The investments required are substantial, but modest compared to the consequences of continuing to lack a full understanding of this critical Earth system process.

Session I: Breaking Ocean Models – When Atmospheric Deposition Goes Extreme

This session addressed limitations in current ocean biogeochemical models when faced with extreme atmospheric deposition events, revealing critical gaps in our understanding of iron cycling processes.

Model Response to Deposition Events:

Atmospheric deposition of aerosols represents one of the largest external nutrient sources to the open ocean, with profound implications for marine productivity, carbon sequestration, and climate feedbacks. Yet, current biogeochemical models demonstrate poor performance when simulating biological responses to extreme aerosol deposition events whether from dust storms, wildfires, or anthropogenic emissions. During major deposition events, most deposited iron is scavenged, precipitated, and sinks to the deep ocean due to supersaturation, bypassing the surface mixed layer where phytoplankton reside – unless organic compounds are present to facilitate cycling within the surface mixed layer. Models struggle particularly with Fe(II), which oxidizes rapidly in seawater and becomes unavailable without organic stabilization. This represents a fundamental challenge: models require organic ligands to keep iron bioavailable, yet they lack mechanistic representations of how these ligands are produced, transported, or delivered alongside atmospheric iron.

Mechanistic Understanding Gaps:

The workshop identified the development of mechanistic links between aerosol deposition and marine biogeochemistry, rather than simply adding tunable parameters, as a key priority for progression. The community consensus was clear: tuning model parameters without mechanistic understanding of the underlying biogeochemical processes creates models that may reproduce historical observations but fail when faced with unprecedented conditions, rendering future projections highly uncertain. As laboratory conditions do not fully represent "real" ocean environments – with their diverse microbial communities, variable organic matter pools, and dynamic physical forcing – coordinating observational campaigns coupled with process studies is essential for building mechanistic understanding.

The diversity of modeling approaches presents additional challenges. Over 20 different ocean biogeochemical (BGC) models are currently in use, each with different sensitivities to trace element deposition fluxes and requiring region-specific validation. These differences arise primarily from divergent assumptions about the magnitude and spatial distribution of iron sources, including aeolian dust, sedimentary, and hydrothermal inputs. Models are often tuned by adjusting iron scavenging rates to reproduce observed seawater iron concentrations, meaning that discrepancies in source assumptions can

produce large uncertainties in the estimated residence time of iron. Furthermore, incomplete understanding of key iron cycling processes in the ocean – such as grazing, particle aggregation, and reactivity – requires re-tuning of plankton growth and loss rates whenever external iron sources change. Changes to one process therefore propagate through other carefully calibrated components, including scavenging parameterizations and ecosystem dynamics, highlighting the interconnected and non-linear nature of marine biogeochemical systems and significantly limiting model capability to predict ecosystem responses to environmental change.

Improved Atmospheric – Ocean Coupling:

Participants identified a disconnect between what atmospheric models can potentially deliver and how ocean models currently use this information. In addition to iron deposition fluxes, atmospheric models can also provide source-specific information about co-deposited organic compounds (that may potentially serve as iron-binding ligands), as well as detailed information on the aerosol size distribution upon deposition – both of which may alter dissolved iron concentrations and lifetime in the ocean. Ocean models typically receive either iron deposition fluxes with variable solubility or particle deposition fluxes from which soluble iron deposition is calculated assuming a fixed solubility, with no representation of the influence of co-deposited organic compounds on iron solubility. The situation becomes more complicated by co-limitation dynamics. When atmospheric deposition alleviates iron limitation, phytoplankton communities may shift to deficiency of other nutrients, such as manganese or phosphorus, based on cellular requirements. This transition illustrates how introducing nutrients to ocean systems can merely transfer the limitation from one macro- or micronutrient to another, rather than boosting overall productivity. Atmospheric models present an opportunity to jointly simulate multiple trace element and nutrient fluxes from various sources (e.g., mineral dust, combustion processes, volcanic activity). However, researchers must strategically select which additional metals warrant inclusion by considering their biogeochemical importance, the role of atmospheric deposition in determining their oceanic bioavailability, and existing constraints on data availability and the current state of understanding of the processes governing their atmospheric cycling, transformation during transport, and post-deposition fate in the ocean.

Data Uncertainties:

Model improvement is severely hampered by fundamental data limitations. Atmospheric deposition estimates carry approximately one order-of-magnitude uncertainty in the (bulk) mass deposited and the resulting aerosol trace element burdens. This uncertainty propagates through to predicted ocean impacts,

making it difficult to determine whether model-observation mismatches reflect poor process representations or uncertain boundary conditions.

Direct measurements of deposition fluxes are rare on oceanographic cruises, which typically focus on water column sampling (potentially influenced by post-deposition advection) rather than atmospheric observations, or with atmospheric observations limited to measuring aerosol concentrations and, less commonly, rain events. This limitation creates substantial challenges in extrapolating the atmospheric concentration data to deposition flux estimates, as the conversion requires knowledge of deposition velocities that vary with particle size, atmospheric conditions, and sea state. Furthermore, conditions measured at a single cruise time and location do not represent the broader regional conditions necessary for model validation and scaling. This spatial heterogeneity is particularly problematic for wet deposition, where extrapolating fluxes from iron concentration and rainfall rate is hampered by the high spatiotemporal variability of precipitation itself. The paucity of long-term observational records compounds these challenges.

These studies are challenging because they require substantial financial commitment from funding agencies to maintain support. On-site personnel, who may not be research scientists, must be trained in proper precautions to maintain sample integrity and minimize potential contamination at long-term monitoring stations. Site selection must also account for prevailing winds and local emission sources, with wind-sector controls used where needed. Without long-term monitoring stations that resolve deposition events on timescales commensurate with phytoplankton response times, capture the full range of deposition magnitudes, and remain free from uncharacterized local signals, models cannot be adequately tested across the conditions they must simulate in climate projections.

Beyond model evaluation, these long-term ground-based records are also essential for validating satellite-derived estimates of atmospheric deposition. In recent years, a growing body of research has sought to retrieve dust transport and deposition from both passive and active satellite observations. These efforts are now extending beyond mineral dust to include long-range transported biomass burning smoke, motivated by emerging evidence that smoke aerosols may also carry bioavailable nutrients capable of stimulating ocean biological productivity. Such satellite-based products offer spatially extensive and temporally resolved, observation-based deposition fields that have the potential to substantially improve model evaluation and to be directly applied in atmospheric–ocean interaction studies. However, the accuracy and reliability of these satellite-derived deposition estimates themselves depend critically on validation against

independent, well-characterized ground-based deposition measurements, underscoring the need for sustained surface monitoring networks.

Path Forward: Priority Actions for the Community

- Develop a more comprehensive mechanistic understanding of organic ligand-iron interactions, including comparison of in-situ ligand production by marine organisms with potential atmospheric inputs, and related photochemical transformations
- Improve understanding of aerosol deposition velocities over the ocean, including their dependencies on particle size and shape, atmospheric stability, boundary layer turbulence and vertical mixing, sea state, and the relative contributions of dry versus wet deposition processes
- Quantify inorganic scavenging processes across the full range of iron concentrations encountered during deposition events, from background levels to supersaturated conditions
- Characterize the biogeochemical reactivity of iron from different aerosol sources (e.g., dust, pyrogenic, volcanic, anthropogenic) to inform source-specific representations of trace element solubility and composition
- Determine how aerosol properties – including size distribution, composition, and mixing state – control atmospheric iron solubility and marine bioavailability upon deposition
- Investigate co-limitation dynamics and cellular stoichiometric requirements for trace metals with significant biogeochemical impact beyond iron (i.e., cobalt, manganese, zinc)
- Compile a comprehensive inventory of ocean biogeochemical models documenting how each model represents key processes controlling metal air-sea fluxes and post-deposition fate – enabling targeted improvements based on identified model strengths and deficiencies
- Develop a reference matrix cataloging available observational and modeling tools with their specifications including temporal resolution, spatial scales, trace elements included, and operational constraints
- Establish long-term time series observations at representative locations that capture both atmospheric deposition and ocean biogeochemical responses at appropriate temporal resolution, with collocated atmospheric and oceanic sampling strongly preferred where logistically feasible
- Develop and deploy instrumentation for direct deposition and Eddy Covariance flux measurements on oceanographic cruises and coastal/insular platforms, rather than relying solely on atmospheric concentration measurements

- Create coupled atmospheric-ocean model testbeds that allow atmospheric models to deliver enhanced information (e.g., source attribution, size distributions, organic aerosol composition) to ocean biogeochemical models at scales and temporal resolutions relevant to biological response
- Better use existing data streams in both atmospheric aerosol samples and seawater – particularly elemental ratio measurements and isotopic ratios – for improved source attribution and validation of atmospheric deposition patterns, using multiple lithogenic tracers simultaneously (Al, Ti, sea-salt-corrected Ca) to provide practical uncertainty estimates
- Support process studies that bridge laboratory investigations and field observations, using mesocosm experiments and natural gradient studies to test mechanistic hypotheses under realistic conditions
- Foster sustained collaboration between atmospheric scientists, chemical oceanographers, and biogeochemical modelers to ensure process representations are consistent with up-to-date observational understanding
- Design coordinated, scale-aware models and experiments jointly between atmospheric and ocean scientists to prevent structural inconsistencies
- Coordinate validation efforts across the diverse suite of ocean BGC models to identify common biases and prioritize process improvements with broad applicability
- Develop community standards for reporting deposition fluxes and bioavailability metrics to enable cross-study synthesis
- Create mechanisms for rapid sharing of deposition event observations to enable opportunistic sampling during extreme events that provide the strongest tests of model capabilities

Addressing these challenges requires a fundamental shift from parameter tuning toward mechanistic understanding – one that can only be achieved through sustained collaboration between atmospheric scientists, oceanographers, and modelers working with shared observational infrastructure and coordinated experimental designs. Reducing the order-of-magnitude uncertainties in deposition fluxes, improving representations of organic ligand dynamics, and expanding direct flux measurements on oceanographic cruises will provide the foundation needed to move beyond models that reproduce historical observations but fail under novel conditions. As atmospheric aerosol sources continue to shift under climate change – with increasing wildfires, changing dust emission patterns, and evolving anthropogenic inputs – the ability to predict ocean biogeochemical responses will depend critically on the process-based understanding that only this kind of integrated, community-wide effort can deliver.

Session II: From Lab to Ocean – Scaling Up Solubility Measurements

This session focused on the challenge of translating laboratory-scale iron solubility measurements to global, real-world biogeochemical processes, revealing methodological opportunities to help fill conceptual understanding research gaps.

Phytoplankton Nutrient Stoichiometry: Beyond Carbon-Based Frameworks

Understanding how much bioavailable iron phytoplankton require under varied physicochemical ocean states depends critically on how we quantify those requirements. Different phytoplankton groups exhibit distinct micronutrient requirements depending on their metabolic pathways and cellular machinery. Iron:Carbon ratios show high variability between different phytoplankton assemblages and species, complicating attempts to predict iron requirements from carbon fixation or biomass estimates alone.

Micronutrient:N (nitrogen) and micronutrient:P (phosphorus) ratios may serve as more reliable indicators for assessing phytoplankton trace element requirements. These ratios exhibit less variability than micronutrient:Carbon ratios because nitrogen and phosphorus are more directly tied to essential cellular components like proteins, nucleic acids, and phospholipids. Examining flexible uptake stoichiometry ratios in relation to the elemental ratios derived by aerosols across different ocean regions and phytoplankton communities could provide a better basis for biogeochemical model parameterization than carbon-based approaches currently employed.

Defining Terms: Solubility, Bioaccessibility, and Bioavailability

The session highlighted a key communication challenge: atmospheric and oceanographic communities often use essential terms differently, leading to confusion when attempting to integrate across disciplines. Solubility, bioaccessibility, and bioavailability are not synonymous, particularly for marine phytoplankton.

Solubility (or dissolved fraction) refers to an operationally defined measurement – the concentration of iron released into solution through a specified extraction method. These methods may involve either passing the solution through a filter of defined pore size or extracting with a specific solvent without filtration, conducted under prescribed chemical conditions using a particular leaching protocol.

Bioaccessibility refers to the potential for iron to be released from its matrix and become available for biological uptake under environmentally relevant conditions. This term includes chemical transformations

that may occur in natural waters, but does not guarantee or explicitly consider the organisms which ultimately use the substance.

Bioavailability represents the fraction of iron that organisms can uptake and use under realistic environmental conditions, accounting for biological processes like active transport, siderophore production, and cellular reduction mechanisms.

These distinctions matter profoundly for model development. Atmospheric models may provide solubility or bioaccessibility estimates, but ocean biogeochemical models require bioavailability information to predict phytoplankton responses. A cross-community discussion is essential to establish a common lexicon where each term is clearly defined and understood across disciplines. More critically, we need frameworks for translating atmospheric measurements of iron solubility into the bioavailability parameters that ocean models require, bridging the conceptual gap between what atmospheric scientists can measure and what oceanographers need for mechanistic understanding.

Laboratory Methods: A Range of Approaches, A Range of Answers:

Current laboratory protocols for quantifying iron solubility vary widely, producing estimates that can differ by orders of magnitude depending on methodology. At one extreme, deionized water (DIW) leaching often provides the lowest estimates, representing iron that dissolves under different pH conditions from seawater without marine organic ligands. At the other extreme, the Berger leach method – using acidified hydroxylamine hydrochloride and heat – is assumed to provide an upper bound estimate of iron solubilization potential, representing the maximum fraction that could eventually be mobilized from aerosol particles through all possible transformation pathways over long timescales, including acid processing, photochemistry, and biological weathering. Between these endpoints lie numerous intermediate approaches (such as using natural filtered seawater, buffer solutions and the addition of organic ligands to seawater), each accessing different fractions of the trace elements contained in aerosol particles.

This methodological diversity creates reproducibility challenges across the research community and complicates efforts to synthesize findings from different studies. However, the variation is not merely a nuisance – it reflects genuine scientific questions about which processes matter in nature. The Berger leach method may lead to overestimates of solubility at the point of deposition, but accounts for potential mechanistic transformations that occur in natural systems over long timescales, including microbial processes that enhance iron release and biological weathering processes that pure chemical solubility tests

miss. Conversely, rapid leaching in DIW or filtered seawater may underestimate iron bioavailability by neglecting biologically-mediated iron release processes that phytoplankton actively employ over long timescales, but do provide an estimate of the amount of iron that may be immediately released into solution upon scavenging by rain or deposition to the sea surface. While all these methods are necessary to obtain a mechanistic understanding of aerosol-derived trace element solubility, variability within similar protocols should be avoided to reduce uncertainty in the produced solubility data.

The challenge is determining which laboratory method – or combination of methods – best represents the processes controlling iron bioavailability in different ocean regions under different conditions. Conversely, we need to identify which biogeochemical processes are actually mimicked by each protocol, recognizing that different methods may be appropriate for different scientific questions or oceanic regions. Without this bidirectional understanding, we cannot confidently translate laboratory solubility measurements into the parameters required by ocean biogeochemical models.

Surface Microlayer: The Critical Interface We Cannot Adequately Sample

Aerosols depositing to the ocean must cross the surface microlayer – an organic-enriched film situated between the ocean and the atmosphere where concentrations of surfactants, exopolymers, and other dissolved organic compounds can be orders of magnitude higher than in underlying waters. Chemical transformations in this layer potentially control the initial speciation and solubility of atmospheric iron deposited, yet our ability to study this critical zone remains severely limited. Surface microlayer experiments present extreme technical difficulties in execution and processing. Actual samples collected using current techniques (glass plates, mesh screens) typically integrate over a much thicker layer than the true surface microlayer being targeted, which exists at the micron-scale where most of the critical chemical processing actually occurs. Surface microlayer sampling is thus complicated by unavoidable dilution with bulk seawater, potentially leading to underestimation of surface chemistry impacts on deposited aerosols. No practical method currently exists for sampling at the sufficient resolution while maintaining chemical integrity. Even if sampling were perfect, the processes are extraordinarily rapid. Chemical species diffuse out of the surface microlayer on time scales of seconds, making it nearly impossible to capture the true chemical signature of surface processes.

Path Forward: Priority Actions for the Community

- Create frameworks for translating atmospheric iron solubility measurements into bioavailability parameters usable by ocean biogeochemical models

- Identify which laboratory leaching protocols best represent specific natural transformation processes under varying atmospheric and oceanic conditions (e.g., cloud processing, oligotrophic vs. eutrophic waters, or different organic matter regimes)
- Develop standard operating procedures for individual leaching methods to reduce uncertainties arising from subtle variations in protocol execution within the same leaching approach
- Investigate specific organic compounds and biological processes that facilitate atmospheric iron release and uptake by phytoplankton
- Evaluate whether Metal:N and Metal:P ratios are more reliable indicators of phytoplankton micronutrient requirements than Metal:C ratios across diverse ocean regions and ecological regimes
- Determine the timescales over which different iron solubilization processes operate in natural systems
- Characterize surface microlayer chemistry and its role in controlling iron speciation from deposited aerosol
- Establish minimum reporting standards and metadata requirements for iron solubility measurements that preserve methodological flexibility while ensuring results can be interpreted and compared across studies
- Create and distribute reference materials for iron and other trace element solubility studies that are compositionally and particle size appropriate, and certified at low mass loadings representative of field-collected filter samples, coordinated through international programs to ensure broad community access
- Support interlaboratory comparison studies that systematically evaluate the uncertainty introduced due to protocol diversity
- Develop improved surface microlayer sampling methodologies that can access micron-scale processes and reduce dilution artifacts, fostering collaboration between surface chemistry specialists, aerosol scientists, and oceanographers
- Create experimental systems that can simulate surface microlayer chemistry under controlled conditions while preserving ecologically relevant chemical complexity
- Create frameworks that foster sustained dialogue between atmospheric and ocean scientists to align measurement approaches with ecological questions
- Develop consensus definitions for solubility, bioaccessibility, and bioavailability through cross-community dialogue and dedicated working groups, with clear operational criteria for each term

- Create mechanisms for rapid dissemination of methodological advances and lessons learned from interlaboratory comparisons

These investments in methodological standardization and cross-community dialogue would transform our ability to translate atmospheric iron solubility measurements into the bioavailability parameters that ocean biogeochemical models require. Progress on consensus terminology, reference materials, and surface microlayer sampling will not only reduce the order-of-magnitude uncertainties that currently plague iron solubility estimates, but will also provide the mechanistic foundation needed to move beyond empirically adjusted parameters toward process-based representations of aerosol iron cycling.

By bridging the conceptual and methodological gap between what atmospheric scientists measure in the laboratory and what oceanographers need to understand phytoplankton responses in the field, the community will be better positioned to project how changing aerosol sources and deposition patterns will alter ocean productivity and carbon cycling under future climate scenarios.

Session III: The Next Generation of Air-Sea Interface Observations

This session explored how novel uses of existing data, combined with emerging observational technologies, could bridge the gap between our understanding of individual processes and the comprehensive observations needed to validate and improve Earth system models.

Temporal and Spatial Resolution: Matching Observations to Process Timescales

Quantifying the daily variability in aerosol emission and transport is essential for capturing episodic deposition events that drive anomalously large phytoplankton blooms. These events—dust storms crossing ocean basins, wildfire plumes spreading across marine regions, volcanic eruptions injecting iron into remote waters—operate on timescales of days to weeks, and are fundamentally different from the seasonal or climatological averages that many observational programs and models emphasize. The appropriate temporal resolution is therefore scientific question-dependent: event attribution and ecosystem responses to pulsed nutrient inputs demand daily or sub-daily output, while climatological applications can tolerate coarser averaging. Beyond biogeochemical applications, operational forecasting of dust events is increasingly important for real-time hazard prediction and human health applications, providing additional motivation for advances in short-timescale atmospheric modeling and improved constraints on deposition velocities.

Spatial resolution requirements similarly vary by application and oceanic region. Basin-scale studies require multiple locations to capture the heterogeneity of deposition patterns, a single-point measurement during a research cruise is insufficient to represent regional variability. While current climate and Earth system models often achieve adequate temporal resolution, they frequently lack the vertical and horizontal spatial detail needed to characterize episodic plume events. This includes resolving the vertical distribution of particles with altitude – a dimension that satellites integrate over the full atmospheric column while surface measurements capture only the lowermost layer – creating a fundamental mismatch that limits meaningful model comparison with field observations.

To address spatiotemporal representativeness, the community requires numerous data points distributed across space and time. Individual in situ stations are unlikely to be able to achieve the required observational density alone. Instead, the community needs a mixed data source initiative that combines autonomous platforms, research vessels, ships of opportunity, satellite observations, and sustained time-series stations to observe both the daily evolution of aerosol deposition events and the resulting phytoplankton responses. This plan represents a fundamental shift from opportunistic sampling toward coordinated observational networks designed to capture process dynamics rather than climatological means.

Atmospheric Input Tracking and Source Attribution:

Source discrimination presents a significant challenge with important implications for understanding ocean biogeochemical responses to dust, wildfire, volcanic, and anthropogenic iron inputs. Anthropogenic sources (industrial emissions, shipping, fossil fuel burning, mining, agriculture) provide more consistent, continuous inputs with chemical signatures and solubility characteristics that, while potentially distinct, remain poorly constrained to date. Natural episodic sources – dust storms, wildfires, volcanic eruptions – deliver large pulses with different temporal signatures and biogeochemical reactivity. Different phytoplankton assemblages may respond differently to these distinct sources and there is no applicable “one size fits all” global approach. Instead, regional and location-specific approaches are required to understand source contributions, their distinct atmospheric signature and their biogeochemical impacts following deposition to the ocean.

Atmospheric inputs can be source-attributed with multiple approaches, including back-trajectory analysis, chemical tracer fingerprinting (elemental ratios, isotopic signatures, organic markers), and integrated modeling approaches. However, these methods often produce inconsistent results, and the community lacks consensus on which approaches work best under different conditions. Back-trajectories depend critically on meteorological reanalysis quality and can accumulate substantial uncertainty over multi-day transport periods. Chemical tracers require comprehensive source characterization libraries that remain incomplete for many regions. While models must be validated against observations, they are limited by the same spatial resolution constraints discussed above. The community needs "plug-and-play" modeling systems where observational data can be readily assimilated to track atmospheric evolution at high spatiotemporal resolution, enabling near-real-time source attribution that can guide adaptive sampling strategies during field campaigns and test mechanistic hypotheses about source-specific biogeochemical responses.

Upper Ocean Response: From Aerosol Deposition to Biological Utilization

A critical knowledge gap exists between measuring atmospheric deposition and observing measurable biological responses. Not all deposited iron becomes bioavailable, and not all bioavailable iron is immediately utilized by phytoplankton. The community needs to distinguish between soluble iron input (what arrives), iron bioaccessibility (what could potentially be taken up), and bioavailability (what phytoplankton actually assimilate and utilize).

Temporal lags between deposition and biological response further complicate attribution. Iron deposition may occur over the course of hours during a dust event, but phytoplankton growth responses emerge over days to weeks as cells acclimate to nutrient availability, assemble the cellular machinery needed for

growth, and undergo population increases. The residence time of aerosol-associated particles in the euphotic zone is a key uncertainty. Furthermore, depending on the time lag between iron deposition and iron utilization by phytoplankton, ocean currents may disperse both phytoplankton and deposited aerosol particles far from the original site of deposition. Hence, satellite chlorophyll observations that show blooms temporally and spatially correlated with aerosol deposition events may reflect actual causation – or may represent coincidental timing with other seasonally prevalent oceanographic processes like upwelling, mixing events, or grazing pressure changes. The phytoplankton community composition underlying these chlorophyll observations from space is currently not well constrained on similar spatiotemporal scales, though next-generation approaches for global, hyperspectral ocean color satellites (e.g., NASA’s PACE mission) aim to fill this gap.

Establishing causative relationships between aerosol deposition and phytoplankton blooms requires converging evidence from multiple observation types: direct measurements of deposition, water column macro- and micronutrient concentrations, physiological indicators of iron limitation relief, and biological productivity metrics. This understanding is critical for Earth system model projections of future changes to ocean carbon uptake. Past attempts to attribute phytoplankton blooms to aerosol fluxes have often relied on simple correlations between aerosol optical depth and ocean color – relationships that may break down under future climate conditions if the correlations do not reflect true causal mechanisms. To generate more robust future projections, models need representations of how deposited iron is processed, how quickly it becomes bioavailable, and how different phytoplankton assemblages utilize different iron forms. Moreover, most existing knowledge and model parameterizations derive from dust observations. We know far less about how phytoplankton respond to wildfire aerosols, volcanic ash, or anthropogenic combustion products – yet these sources are changing rapidly under climate change and may become increasingly important in some regions. Each source delivers different iron species, particle sizes, and co-deposited compounds that may alter bioavailability and biological responses in ways current models do not currently capture.

Satellite Data Integration and Critical Observational Gaps:

Current satellite capabilities miss critical processes occurring at the air-sea interface. Satellites cannot observe surface microlayer processes, cannot capture sub-daily variability in deposition or biological responses using polar orbiting sensors, and cannot detect small-scale spatial heterogeneity (including vertical heterogeneity) that occurs below a satellite’s swath resolution. Some of these deposition events inherently obscure the ocean color signal and result in surface ocean data gaps during wildfires, volcanic

eruptions, and large-scale dust storms. These are not minor details but fundamental limitations that prevent satellites from observing the processes that control whether deposited iron enhances ocean productivity.

Integration of multiple satellite products offers partial solutions. Combining aerosol optical depth from multiple sensors with ocean color, sea surface temperature, wind fields, and precipitation can provide more comprehensive characterization of atmospheric inputs and ocean responses. Machine learning approaches may extract relationships from these multi-sensor datasets that individual products miss. However, these approaches rely on correlations and may not capture mechanistic processes, particularly for novel conditions (e.g., emergence of new emission sources, unprecedented dust storms or wildfire outbreaks, future climate states that fundamentally alter landscapes, chemistry, or transport pathways) where historical correlations may not hold. Real-time or near-real-time satellite data could improve model prediction capabilities by enabling data assimilation that corrects atmospheric transport errors and guides adaptive sampling. A low-earth-orbit geostationary satellite constellation network – though currently not available for most relevant parameters – could provide the high temporal resolution needed to track rapid atmospheric evolution and detect ephemeral deposition events that current polar-orbiting satellites miss.

Yet satellites alone cannot solve the observational challenge. They must be integrated with in situ observations that provide the mechanistic understanding and direct measurements of processes that satellites cannot observe. The future lies in coordinated observing systems that leverage each platform's strengths: satellites for spatial coverage and temporal continuity, autonomous platforms for sustained time-series in key locations, research vessels for detailed process studies, and aircraft for vertical profiling of both atmospheric and upper ocean properties.

Path Forward: Priority Actions for the Community

- Determine temporal resolution requirements most suitable for different scientific applications – which questions require daily data versus climatological averages, and how requirements vary across ocean regions and seasons
- Develop and expand methods to establish causative rather than correlative relationships between atmospheric deposition and biological responses – while physiological indicators of iron limitation relief exist, their routine deployment on autonomous platforms such as BGC-Argo floats remains limited, constraining our ability to distinguish iron-driven responses from other growth drivers at basin scales

- Characterize how phytoplankton assemblages respond differently to distinct aerosol sources (e.g., dust, wildfire, volcanic, anthropogenic emissions), moving beyond the dust-centric understanding that dominates current literature
- Quantify temporal lags between deposition and biological responses for different phytoplankton groups, iron sources, and oceanographic conditions
- Understand how deposited iron is processed in the upper ocean: transformation rates, loss pathways, and the timescales over which bioavailability evolves after deposition
- Develop a Science Prioritization Matrix for satellite-observable metrics that can distinguish between different iron sources and their biogeochemical impacts, ranking measurement requirements by scientific value, feasibility, and technology readiness to guide future satellite mission development
- Develop adaptive observational approaches that capture episodic atmospheric events with appropriate spatiotemporal sampling while maintaining efficient resource use
- Create comprehensive observational programs integrating atmospheric, air-sea interface, and upper ocean biological measurements to track the full aerosol pathway from emission to biological utilization
- Establish modular modeling frameworks where observational data – including satellite-derived aerosol products, shipboard trace element measurements, and autonomous platform data – can be systematically assimilated to track atmospheric evolution, attribute sources, and test process hypotheses
- Deploy mixed-platform observation networks combining autonomous systems, sustained time-series stations, research vessels, and satellite observations to achieve required spatiotemporal coverage
- Develop integrated satellite products that combine aerosol, ocean color, meteorological, and oceanographic observations to characterize deposition events and biological responses
- Support development of machine learning approaches that can extract mechanistic insights from multi-sensor datasets while maintaining physical interpretability for model development
- Establish aircraft-based observational capabilities for vertical profiling of atmospheric composition and upper ocean properties during deposition events
- Design integrated observational strategies with inputs from atmospheric scientists, satellite remote sensing specialists, oceanographers, and modelers

- Develop protocols for rapid response to episodic deposition events, enabling coordinated sampling across platforms when forecasts or real-time observations detect major atmospheric transport events
- Create data sharing frameworks that make observational data rapidly available to the modeling community for assimilation and process study
- Establish working groups to develop consensus approaches for source attribution using chemical tracers, back-trajectories, and modeling, with systematic intercomparison of methods
- Coordinate validation of satellite products against in-situ observations across diverse ocean regions and deposition event types
- Build sustained international partnerships to achieve basin-scale observational coverage, recognizing that no single nation or agency can deploy sufficient infrastructure alone

Realizing this vision requires moving beyond opportunistic sampling and isolated observational efforts toward coordinated, multi-platform networks designed to capture process dynamics from atmospheric emission to biological utilization. Progress on source attribution methods, temporal resolution requirements, and causative deposition-response relationships will provide the observational foundation that Earth system models urgently need. By integrating satellite coverage, autonomous platforms, research vessels, and aircraft into coherent observing systems – and by fostering sustained collaboration across the atmospheric, oceanographic, and remote sensing communities – we can transform our understanding of how aerosol deposition shapes ocean productivity and carbon cycling under present and future climate conditions.

Session IV: A Community Model Intercomparison Project (MIP)

This session focused on developing a coordinated community effort to systematically compare and evaluate iron-cycling representations across atmospheric and oceanic models. Participants identified a structured Model Intercomparison Project as essential for quantifying uncertainties, diagnosing systematic biases, and accelerating progress toward robust simulations of iron-driven biogeochemical responses.

Atmospheric Model Resolution and Validation:

The session addressed fundamental questions about spatial and temporal resolution requirements for atmospheric models to serve ocean biogeochemistry applications adequately. While high-resolution atmospheric models exist, systematic validation is needed to ensure dust and other aerosols are deposited in the correct oceanic regions with appropriate temporal characteristics. Current models may achieve reasonable spatial accuracy but often lack the daily temporal resolution essential for capturing episodic deposition events that drive anomalous biological responses.

Basin-scale studies require multiple observation points to achieve adequate spatial coverage, as single-location measurements cannot capture the heterogeneity of deposition patterns. Optimal resolution requirements vary by application and region – some scientific questions demand daily or sub-daily data, while others can utilize climatological averages – with the resolution tuned to the specific research question of interest. The challenge lies in balancing computational costs with scientific requirements while ensuring models capture the processes that matter for ocean biogeochemistry.

Process-Based Model Integration:

A process-based understanding of mechanisms is essential to bridge the gap between observations and model representation. This requires the active participation of laboratory experimentalists in workshops to improve model parameterizations and integrate new understanding of air-sea interface processes into existing models. The workshop identified that progress will rely on developing mechanistic links between aerosol deposition and marine biogeochemistry, rather than simply adding tunable parameters that may reproduce historical data but fail under novel conditions.

The diversity of modeling approaches presents additional challenges, with over 20 different ocean biogeochemical models currently in use, each with different sensitivities to trace element deposition and requiring region-specific validation. Modifications to one process often cascade through these

interconnected systems, highlighting the need for comprehensive validation datasets and systematic intercomparison efforts.

Proposed MIP Framework and Implementation:

The community outlined an ambitious framework for a trace element MIP that would leverage CMIP7 infrastructure and protocols. The proposed approach includes both historical simulations (1980–2023 using reanalysis meteorology) and future projections using standardized emission scenarios. A critical innovation involves creating a reference database of trace metal emissions and deposition fields that would be freely available to the wider modeling community.

Atmospheric models would first generate multi-model deposition fields validated against observational datasets contributed by the community. These validated atmospheric outputs would then drive ocean biogeochemical models from pre-industrial conditions (1750) through future scenarios, enabling assessment of how changing atmospheric patterns affect marine ecosystems across temporal scales. The synthesis of multi-model outputs would create an open database serving diverse research communities beyond the core MIP participants.

Standardization and Protocol Development:

Standardized simulation protocols – analogous to successful frameworks like GEOTRACES (An International Study of the Marine Biogeochemical Cycles of Trace Elements and Their Isotopes) or AerChemMIP (Aerosols and Chemistry Model Intercomparison Project) – are essential for enabling meaningful cross-model comparisons. This includes common scenarios for model experiments, agreed-upon metrics for performance evaluation, and systematic approaches for uncertainty quantification. Specific protocol requirements identified include standardized model simulation experiments – prescribing common forcing fields, initial conditions, emission scenarios, and output diagnostics to ensure that inter-model differences reflect process representations rather than differences in experimental setup – benchmark datasets from coordinated field campaigns, and quality control procedures ensuring cross-model comparability.

Integration with Climate Projections:

A major opportunity identified was incorporating atmospheric nutrient deposition into CMIP7 climate projections, potentially transforming how Earth system models represent biogeochemical feedbacks. The session highlighted the need to identify climate-sensitive regions where changing deposition patterns

could have disproportionate impacts on ocean productivity and carbon cycling. At the same time, changing ocean properties will influence the fate of deposited nutrients – increasing stratification will modify nutrient utilization, while ocean acidification and shifts in organic matter cycling will alter the solubility and bioavailability of deposited trace metals. Predicting future ocean carbon uptake therefore requires a fully coupled system that incorporates emission-driven changes in both the atmosphere and ocean, alongside marine biogeochemical responses to changing atmospheric nutrient sources.

Path Forward: Priority Actions for the Community

- Establish quantitative relationships between model resolution and ability to capture episodic deposition events that drive biological responses
- Develop mechanistic representations that translate laboratory findings into model formulations valid across diverse ocean conditions
- Quantify how ocean stratification changes will modify biological utilization of atmospherically-deposited nutrients
- Create uncertainty quantification frameworks that distinguish between parametric, structural, and forcing uncertainties
- Develop a comprehensive reference database of trace metal emissions and deposition for community use
- Create model testbeds where observational data can be rapidly assimilated to evaluate process representations
- Establish benchmark datasets from coordinated field campaigns spanning different oceanic regimes
- Support development of standardized analysis tools for model-observation comparisons
- Foster sustained collaboration between experimentalists, observationalists, and modelers to ensure process representations reflect current understanding
- Develop modular model architectures and community protocols that allow new process understanding – from laboratory experiments and field observations – to be systematically evaluated and integrated into operational biogeochemical models
- Coordinate proposal development for large-scale, multi-institutional model intercomparison project (MIP) implementation
- Establish working groups for protocol standardization following successful examples from GEOTRACES
- Develop international partnerships to ensure global participation and data sharing

A coordinated trace element MIP represents one of the highest-leverage investments the community can make – not only quantifying uncertainties and diagnosing systematic model biases, but also creating shared infrastructure, reference datasets, and standardized protocols that will benefit the broader Earth system modeling community for decades. By leveraging CMIP7 frameworks and building on successful precedents like GEOTRACES and AerChemMIP, this effort can transform fragmented modeling activities into a coherent, community-wide enterprise capable of delivering the robust, process-based projections that policy-relevant climate assessments require.

Session V: Satellite Integration and Future Technologies

This final session examined where current observational capabilities fall short, which new technologies show promise, and how the community must expand to leverage these opportunities.

Current Satellite Limitations: What We Cannot See

Dust retrievals from satellites require significant improvement for oceanographic applications. Passive satellite sensors retrieve column-integrated aerosol properties, provide no nighttime data, and cannot easily separate dust from other aerosol types in mixed plumes – a critical limitation since different aerosol sources have distinct iron content, solubility, and biogeochemical impacts. Active sensors like CALIPSO address some of these limitations by providing aerosol type discrimination and vertical profiles of extinction and backscatter, enabling identification of dust layers and their altitude – essential for estimating deposition. However, active sensors have an extremely limited spatial footprint, sampling only narrow swaths. This means CALIPSO may entirely miss dust plumes that are spatially offset from its ground track, providing excellent vertical detail for features it observes but leaving vast regions unsampled. Compounding this spatial limitation, CALIPSO ceased operations on August 1, 2023 after nearly two decades of observations. This has left a significant gap in spaceborne lidar coverage for dust vertical profiling. Sustained global coverage will not be fully restored until successor missions such as EarthCARE become operational.

Satellite products become extremely noisy when approaching the surface ocean interface – precisely where most critical air-sea exchange processes occur. Surface reflection contaminates aerosol retrievals in the lowest atmospheric layers. Atmospheric boundary layer effects, including humidity gradients and particle hygroscopic growth, alter aerosol optical properties in ways that confound retrieval algorithms. Sea surface roughness affects both atmospheric and ocean retrievals. The result is that satellites are least reliable exactly where we most need accurate observations: at the interface where aerosols deposit and iron enters the ocean.

Satellite retrievals are based on backscattered radiation and cannot directly constrain aerosol trace metal concentrations, chemical speciation, or the soluble and bioavailable fractions of iron that determine biological impact. Aerosol aging processes during atmospheric transport – which can significantly alter iron solubility through acid processing, photochemistry, and cloud interactions – are not detectable from current satellite measurements. Satellites capture atmospheric snapshots at specific time points, failing to track the continuous chemical and physical transformations that unfold during multi-day aerosol transport across ocean basins. Most critically, satellites detect atmospheric concentrations rather than deposition

fluxes – they reveal what remains airborne, not what enters the ocean. Nevertheless, researchers have developed methods to derive long-term three-dimensional dust concentrations and deposition fluxes from satellite observations. Developing and refining algorithms that translate satellite-observed atmospheric properties into ocean deposition rates remains a key research priority. Equally important is establishing direct dust flux measurements at remote island monitoring stations to complement existing concentration measurements. These ground-based flux collections would provide essential validation data for satellite-derived deposition estimates and help constrain the algorithms that convert atmospheric observations into surface fluxes.

Emerging Technologies and Opportunities:

Despite these challenges, emerging satellite capabilities offer new pathways forward. Hyperspectral satellite products show promise for detecting iron content in aerosols by analyzing detailed spectral features that broadband sensors miss. Current hyperspectral retrievals are noisy and lack sufficient ground-truth validation, but the underlying physics is sound: different iron-bearing minerals have distinct spectral signatures that could enable both iron quantification and mineralogical characterization. The Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation (EMIT) mission exemplifies this potential, providing spatially resolved soil mineralogy at high resolution to characterize iron content and mineral form in dust source regions. This enables improved source apportionment – determining not just that dust is present, but whether it originated from Saharan, Asian, Australian, or South American sources, each with distinct iron mineralogy and solubility characteristics. Since iron mineral form determines its susceptibility to dissolution during transport, such observationally constrained source characterization is particularly valuable for atmospheric models estimating soluble iron deposition to the ocean.

Machine learning algorithms could potentially connect satellite aerosol observations with surface ocean biogeochemical responses. However, such approaches would require extensive training datasets combining satellite and in-situ measurements – a significant limitation given the sparsity of in-water matchups available for algorithm development and validation. Empirical approaches that relate hyperspectral reflectance to biogeochemical properties, such as those being implemented for phytoplankton community composition with the PACE mission, demonstrate the potential of ocean color data for extracting biological information, but are themselves constrained by the limited availability of coincident in-situ observations needed to extend them to global scales.

Geostationary satellites offer fundamentally different capabilities than current polar-orbiting systems. With continuous viewing of the same region, geostationary platforms can track aerosol plume evolution

at hourly timescales, capturing diurnal cycles and rapid transport events that polar orbiters sample only once or twice daily. For atmospheric deposition studies, this temporal resolution could transform our ability to observe dust storm evolution, wildfire plume transport, and the timing of deposition events relative to ocean biological responses. However, current geostationary systems focus primarily on meteorology and carry limited aerosol retrieval capabilities – expanding these capabilities requires dedicated next-generation missions. A deeper challenge lies in the mismatch between the timescales at which models and satellite products are validated and those at which biologically meaningful deposition events occur. Without sufficient surface measurements at daily or sub-daily resolution, model and satellite products can only be validated against monthly to seasonal averages – a temporal scale that is too coarse to capture individual deposition events and their associated ocean biological responses. Bridging this gap requires transitioning from satellite-derived products to model frameworks capable of resolving daily deposition fluxes. Future geostationary lidar missions – particularly those employing High Spectral Resolution Lidar (HSRL) technology – could play a critical role in this validation chain, providing continuous, aerosol-type-resolved observations at hourly timescales that resolve individual deposition events and their temporal evolution, constraining both satellite-derived deposition products and model frameworks at timescales commensurate with ocean biological response times.

Community Expansion: Bridging Disciplinary Gaps

The session identified critical gaps in current research networks that limit progress. Process-based modelers who can translate satellite observables into mechanistic biogeochemical understanding are needed to ensure satellite data informs, rather than just correlates with, ocean responses. BGC-Argo experts can leverage autonomous profiling float capabilities to provide some of the in situ validation data that satellite products desperately need, but integrating these communities requires sustained collaboration and coordination. Further, the task of comparing between satellite-derived proxies and float-derived proxies is not trivial, particularly on global scales across ecosystems and optical regimes.

The interdisciplinary expertise gap may be the most consequential barrier to progress. Atmospheric scientists understand aerosol optical properties and transport but may lack familiarity with marine biogeochemistry. Oceanographers understand phytoplankton physiology and iron limitation but may not appreciate atmospheric processing during transport. Satellite remote sensing specialists can extract information from radiance data but need guidance on which products serve biogeochemical questions. Bridging these communities requires not just workshops but sustained collaborative projects where researchers work together on shared datasets and common scientific questions.

Path Forward: Priority Actions for the Community

- Quantify how different aerosol types and mixing states (e.g., marine, volcanic ash, pure dust, dust-smoke mixtures, pollution aerosols) can be distinguished in satellite retrievals over the ocean, and determine accuracy requirements for biogeochemical applications
- Develop relationships between satellite-observable properties (e.g., aerosol optical depth, spectral signatures, vertical profiles) and biogeochemically-relevant properties (e.g., iron content and solubility, source attribution, phytoplankton community composition)
- Understand how aerosol aging during transport alters iron bioavailability and determine whether observable proxies exist for different aging states
- Characterize signal-to-noise requirements for detecting biologically meaningful deposition events, accounting for the diversity of aerosol sources – including dust, anthropogenic aerosols, and volcanic ash – whose distinct iron mineralogy, solubility, and seasonal variability will influence detectability across different ocean regions
- Establish whether machine learning relationships between satellite aerosols and ocean responses remain valid under future or historical climate conditions not represented in training data
- Support validation campaigns that provide ground-truth measurements for emerging satellite products, particularly hyperspectral aerosol retrievals and iron content estimates
- Develop standardized protocols for comparing satellite retrievals to in situ aerosol and deposition measurements, accounting for spatial and temporal representativeness mismatches
- Create integrated satellite–in situ datasets combining aerosol properties, deposition measurements, and ocean biogeochemical responses to train and validate machine learning algorithms
- Establish a Science Prioritization Matrix for satellite observables that can distinguish iron sources and their biogeochemical impacts, translating scientific requirements into prioritized measurement capabilities to guide future satellite mission development
- Support development of next-generation geostationary aerosol capabilities that provide high temporal resolution observations of atmospheric transport and deposition events
- Invest in hyperspectral satellite missions capable of detecting phytoplankton communities, iron-bearing minerals, and potentially quantifying bioavailable iron content
- Deploy BGC-Argo floats strategically in regions where satellite aerosol retrievals are poorest – including the high-latitude Southern Ocean, coastal regions, and tropical systems – to provide in situ validation data on biogeochemical responses to aerosol deposition

- Conduct a comprehensive community survey to map existing expertise and identify critical gaps across atmospheric science, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and remote sensing
- Create sustained interdisciplinary collaborations bringing together atmospheric scientists, oceanographers, modelers, and satellite specialists to work on shared datasets and common scientific questions
- Establish working groups focused on translating satellite aerosol products into inputs usable by ocean biogeochemical models
- Foster partnerships between satellite missions (EMIT, PACE, TEMPO, and future missions) and oceanographic observing programs to ensure validation data collection and product development serve both communities
- Recruit and train early-career researchers in interdisciplinary skills spanning atmosphere-ocean interactions, remote sensing, and biogeochemical modeling
- Connect BGC-Argo experts with atmospheric deposition researchers to coordinate float deployments that maximize validation value for satellite products
- Develop educational materials and workshops that build cross-disciplinary literacy, enabling more effective collaboration across atmospheric, oceanographic, and remote sensing communities

These investments in satellite capabilities, interdisciplinary collaboration, and integrated observing infrastructure would fundamentally advance our ability to track atmospheric aerosol sources, transport, and deposition at the spatial and temporal scales that matter for ocean biogeochemistry. Progress on hyperspectral retrievals, geostationary monitoring, and machine learning frameworks – validated by coordinated BGC-Argo and ground-based observations – will help close the critical gap between what satellites can observe in the atmosphere and what oceanographers need to understand at the air-sea interface. By expanding the community to bridge atmospheric science, remote sensing, and marine biogeochemistry, and by prioritizing the next generation of satellite missions with explicit biogeochemical objectives, the field will be better equipped to detect, attribute, and ultimately predict how shifting aerosol deposition patterns under future climate scenarios will reshape ocean productivity, nutrient cycling, and carbon sequestration on a global scale.

Lead Authors

Nicholas Meskhidze, North Carolina State University, USA (nmeskhi@ncsu.edu)

Douglas Hamilton, North Carolina State University, USA (dshamil3@ncsu.edu)

Morgane Perron, University of Brest, France (morgane.perron@univ-brest.fr)

Akinori Ito, JAMSTEC, Japan (akinorii@jamstec.go.jp)

Contributors

51 contributors listed alphabetically by last name

Last Name	First Name	Affiliation	Email
Bates	Eleanor	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	esbates@hawaii.edu
Bergas-Masso	Elisa	NC State University	ebergas@ncsu.edu
Bhattacharyya	Rohan	CSIR NIO, Goa, India	iamrohan1992@gmail.com
Bisson	Kelsey	NASA's Ocean Biology and Biogeochemistry (OBB) program	kelsey.bisson@nasa.gov
Bowie	Andrew	University of Tasmania	Andrew.Bowie@utas.edu.au
Buchanan	Pearse	CSIRO, Australia	Pearse.Buchanan@csiro.au
Buck	Clifton	Skidaway Institute of Oceanography, University of Georgia	clifton.buck@skio.uga.edu
Bunnell	Zach	University of South Florida	zbunnell@usf.edu
Capone	Dante	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, UC San Diego	dcapone@ucsd.edu
Chaki	Debasmita	CSIR National Institute of Oceanography, Goa, India	debasmitachaki295@gmail.com
Conway	Tim	University of South Florida	tmconway@usf.edu
Cosentino	Nicolas	CIMA-IFAECI (CONICET-UBA-CNRS-IRD), Buenos Aires	nicolas.cosentino@cima.fcen.uba.ar
Croot	Peter	University of Galway, Ireland	peter.croot@nuigalway.ie
Dinasquet	Julie	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, UC San Diego	jdinasquet@ucsd.edu
Elliott	Hope	Wittenberg University	elliott@wittenberg.edu

Last Name	First Name	Affiliation	Email
Feng	Yan	Argonne National Laboratory	yfeng@anl.gov
Fietz	Susanne	Stellenbosch University	sfietz@sun.ac.za
Floback	Alexis	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	floback@hawaii.edu
Gao	Yuan	Rutgers University–Newark	yuangaoh@newark.rutgers.edu
Garraway	Chaz	Northeastern University	garraway.c@northeastern.edu
Gonçalves Ageitos	María	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya / Barcelona Supercomputing Center	maria.goncalves@bsc.es
Guieu	Cecile	Laboratoire Oceanographie Villefranche sur Mer, France	cecile.guieu@imev-mer.fr
Ho	Tung-Yuan	Academia Sinica, Taiwan	tyho@sinica.edu.tw
Hsieh	Chih-Chiang	Academia Sinica, Taiwan	tyho@gate.sinica.edu.tw
Ito	Takamatsu	Georgia Institute of Technology	taka.ito@eas.gatech.edu
Kollman	Charlotte	Skidaway Institute of Oceanography, University of Georgia	charlotte.kollman@uga.edu
Kramer	Sasha	MBARI (postdoc; starting July 1: Boston University, Assistant Professor)	sashajane19@gmail.com
Kumar	Ashwini	National Institute of Oceanography, India	ashwinik@nio.org
Landing	Bill	Florida State University	wlanding@fsu.edu
Li	Wenshuai	Ocean University of China	lws@stu.ouc.edu.cn
Mattin	Alex	Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand	alexander.mattin@vuw.ac.nz
Ohnemus	Daniel	Skidaway Institute of Oceanography, University of Georgia	dohnemus@gmail.com
Panda	Prema	CSIR NIO, Goa, India	premapiyushap@gmail.com
Qi	Yuxuan	Ocean University of China	qyx2034@stu.ouc.edu.cn
Ren	Xuelin		15735407917@163.com
Richon	Camille	Laboratoire des Sciences de l'Environnement Marin, France	camille.richon@univ-brest.fr
Romm	Matthew	NC State University	mromm@ncsu.edu

Last Name	First Name	Affiliation	Email
Scharle	Phoebe	University of Miami	phoebe.scharle@earth.miami.edu
Shi	Yingxi	Chinese University of Hong Kong	shixianzhai@cuhk.edu.hk
Shi	Yang	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	yangshi25120@gmail.com
Sonar	Aditya	NC State University	ajsonar@ncsu.edu
Song	Yaoyu	State Key Laboratory of Physical Oceanography, Ocean University of China	1193971248@qq.com
Tang	Mingjin	Guangzhou Institute of Geochemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences	mingjintang@126.com
Winton	Holly	Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand	holly.winton@vuw.ac.nz
Wozniak	Andrew	University of Delaware	awozniak@udel.edu
Wang	Xinshuo	Ocean University of China	1306018853@qq.com
Xokashe	Sive	University of Tasmania	sive.xokashe@utas.edu.au
Ye	Ying	Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	Ying.Ye@awi.de
Zhang	Tianyu	Guangzhou Institute of Geochemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences	zhangtianyu@gig.ac.cn
Zhang	Yifan	Guangzhou Institute of Geochemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences	zhangyifan@gig.ac.cn
Zhou	Yang	Ocean University of China	yangzhou@ouc.edu.cn